

Investors' reaction to the introduction of new ESG indexes: evidence from an event study approach

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ABSTRACT: The intention behind this contribution is to explore how the market, particularly investors, reacts to the reinforcement announcement of the MASI-ESG index using event study methodology. The study is conducted over two years, running from January 2, 2022, to December 31, 2023. It includes 21 days, 10 days before the announcement of five new additions to the MASI-ESG index on January 24, 2023, and extends for 10 days following that date. It focuses on how environmental scores affect stock prices in the short term. The conclusions of this paper indicate that investors exhibit a very short-term reaction immediately after the announcement of the event under investigation, showcasing abnormal returns observed at various dates within the selected timeframe. The same observation goes against the semi-strong form of the efficient market hypothesis if we consider the test carried out in this research as an appropriate tool to assess its validity. The study also emphasizes the importance of adopting long-term perspectives to understand the true impact on stock prices, analyzing synergies and their influence on the financial health of constituent companies.

Key-words: Corporate social responsibility, financial performance, event study methodology, informational efficiency, Moroccan financial market.

1. Introduction

Presently, intangible assets, notably reputation, are gaining prominence in gauging a company's value, while concurrently, firms encounter heightened demands regarding their environmental and social responsibilities. Corporations are urged to seek out innovative business models, novel product offerings, and alternative strategies to mitigate carbon emissions, shrink their operational environmental footprint, and actively contribute to the welfare of communities. The predominant trend among firms is to pursue sustainability endeavors to fortify their reputations and uphold societal approval for their operations (Robinson et al., 2011). To put it another way, participating in social welfare efforts or donating to societal causes can positively impact companies' financial standing, reputation, and reinforce both brand images and corporate identities. These actions are perceived positively by consumers and are also attractive to institutional investors (Wang and Chen, 2017).

Recently, there has been a surge in companies asserting their dedication to social responsibility by joining CSR initiatives, associating themselves with the CSR designation, and integrating CSR reports into their annual reports (Curran and Moran, 2007). The purpose of this research is to assess how a company's CSR efforts influence its financial performance, focusing on the company's share price as an indicator. To quantify the impact of CSR on share price, we employed an event study methodology, which tracks fluctuations in share prices triggered by event announcements. Assessing the financial repercussions of new information on a company's share price is facilitated through event studies, which are based on the premise of market efficiency. In accordance with the semi-strong form of market efficiency, the share prices of relevant firms will promptly reflect any new information.

Numerous studies have delved into the relationship between corporate social responsibility (CSR) and financial performance, employing a wide array of econometric methodologies. Margolis and Walsh (2001), along with Martin Curran (2003), have conducted comprehensive reviews of these studies, offering valuable insights into the nuanced findings and methodologies employed across the academic landscape. The conventional method of evaluating CSR involves the use of proxies; however, in our study, we employed announcements from constituents of the (MASI-ESG) Index as our CSR proxy. The creation of this index aimed to simplify investment in socially conscious companies.

Event studies are commonly applied to illustrate the relationship between news or events and fluctuations in stock prices. They seek to depict how the market, analysts, and investors respond to favorable and unfavorable news related to specific companies. Typically, a company's stock price decreases in response to negative news, while it increases in reaction to positive news coverage. Generally, the fluctuation in the stock price will level off again within hours or days, depending on the seriousness of the matter. Usually, unless it's severely adverse news such as a company entering liquidation or bankruptcy, stories do not have a lasting impact in the long run (Curran and Moran, 2007).

Morocco's Casablanca Stock Exchange launched the Casablanca ESG-10 in 2018, and it has recently transitioned into MASI-ESG, growing from 10 to 15 securities. Its primary objective is to highlight the commitment and CSR practices of companies listed on the financial market. The goal of this paper is to analyze how the market, particularly investors, reacts to a specific event, specifically the announcement of the reinforcement of the MASI-ESG index. It employs the event study methodology to evaluate how environmental scores affect stock prices in the short term surrounding the announcement.

This manuscript is structured into five sections, encompassing the introduction and conclusion. The second section offers a thorough analysis of the literature review, while the third section elaborates on the methodology employed, specifically focusing on the event study. In the fourth section, we provide an overview of the data and present the empirical results.

2. Literature review

An in-depth examination of the corporate social responsibility literature has shown that research on this subject is organized into three distinct categories. Firstly, one category focuses on analyzing the impact of CSR practices on accounting performance measures. Secondly, another category endeavors to shed light on the effects of CSR practices on long-term market performance measures. Finally, the third category explores the influence of CSR practices on short-term fluctuations in stock prices, using the commonly known methodology of event studies (Wang and Chen, 2017).

Curran and Moran's (2007) study, investigating how companies' inclusion in the FTSE4Good index affects financial performance, suggested that the announcement triggers both anticipated negative and positive effects on daily returns. Nonetheless, it's crucial to highlight that these fluctuations are statistically insignificant, and the data strongly indicate that being listed in the FTSE4Good index doesn't necessarily lead to noteworthy financial returns.

In 2009, Arya and Zhang undertook research to explore how the timing of CSR announcements from companies adhering to new social regulations in South Africa has impacted stock prices. For this purpose, the researchers opted to conduct an event study utilizing a unique dataset of South African publicly traded companies that had implemented CSR initiatives between 1996 and 2005. The results suggest that investors respond favorably to CSR announcements made during the later stages of institutional reforms. Moreover, CSR announcements accompanied by substantial monetary value yield notably higher returns in the stock market.

Within the same timeframe (2009), Consolandi et al. published a scientific paper with a dual objective. At first, the two scholars examined the performance of the DJSSI from 2001 to 2006 in comparison to the Surrogate Complementary Index (SCI). This new index consisted solely of components from the DJ Stoxx 600 that were not included in the ethical index. The purpose was to achieve a more comprehensive diagnosis of potential performance variations. Secondly, the authors performed an event study on the same dataset to ascertain whether the stock market assessment reacts to inclusion (or deletion) in the DJSSI. The observations in both scenarios indicate that evaluating a company's CSR performance is a critical aspect of asset allocation activities.

Back in 2010, Artiach et al. released their investigation entitled "The determinants of corporate sustainability performance." Their goal was to investigate the factors motivating American companies to embrace sustainability principles and to develop multiple hypotheses connecting corporate sustainability performance (CSP) with particular company attributes. Based on the findings, it is evident that prominent firms in the realm of CSP exhibit notably larger size, undergo greater levels of growth, and attain a superior return on equity compared to conventional companies. Conversely, companies distinguished by CSP do not demonstrate higher available cash flows or lower leverage compared to their counterparts.

During February 2013, Cheung and Roca aimed to investigate the effects on returns, risk, and liquidity of stocks in the Asia-Pacific markets when they were included in or excluded from the Dow Jones Sustainability World Index between 2002 and 2010. The conclusions indicate that both newly added and removed stocks experienced a significant decline in returns, an uptick in trading volume, stability in systematic risk, and an increase in idiosyncratic risk. Essentially, investors in the Asia-Pacific region responded differently compared to those in Europe and the United States regarding corporate sustainability matters.

Second to last, Schaeffer et al. (2012) examine how the stock value of a specific group of oil companies, which are members of the Dow Jones Sustainability Index (DJSI World), is affected. To do so, it evaluates the fluctuations of three indicators, namely: 1) the systemic risk of the selected companies (beta), 2) the responsiveness of their stock prices to changes in crude oil prices, and 3) the conditional variance of their stock prices (volatility). According to the results, only two companies saw their betas decrease following their inclusion in the DJSI, and no changes in volatility or correlation with oil prices were observed for any of the companies. Thus, there still remains a lack of statistically conclusive evidence regarding a net positive impact between the adoption of a proactive environmental approach by oil companies, as reflected by their inclusion in the DJSI, and the movement of their stock prices.

Finally, Inoue and Lee (2011) analyze how five dimensions of corporate social responsibility—employee relations, product quality, community engagement, environmental issues, and diversity—affect the financial performance of companies within four sectors of the tourism industry: airlines, casinos, hotels, and restaurants. While it was expected that all dimensions of CSR would have positive financial effects, the results showed that each dimension had a differentiated impact on short and long-term profitability, and these financial effects varied across the four industries. The outcomes indicate that CSR has a significantly adverse impact on the short-term finances of airlines, without any long-term effect on firm value. On the flip side, the authors noted significantly positive effects of CSR, both short and long-term, on hotels and restaurants.

2.1. The CSR index in Morocco

The table n°1 presents the 15 stocks that have been incorporated into the MASI-ESG index after the introduction of 5 new securities. In this context, it's worth noting that the index was established to fulfill the requirements regarding corporate social responsibility. The index's development relies on non-financial criteria encompassing indicators utilized in a calculation method known as ESG rating, which aims to measure companies' efforts in areas related to the environment, social framework compliance, and governance.

Table n°1: List of securities included in the MASI-ESG index (the day of the announcement of new introductions¹)

	IPO date	Sectors	Consolidated accounts	Equity (2022)	Number of securities (2022)
BMCI	28/02/1972	Banks	Yes	7.651.634.000,00	13.279.286
BOA	16/06/1975	Banks	Yes	27.980.530.000,00	205.606.648
AWB	13/08/1943	Banks	Yes	54.292.985.000,00	209.859.679
BCP	06/07/2004	Banks	Yes	47.473.195.000,00	202.254.656
CIH	23/06/1967	Banks	Yes	5.846.695.000,00	28.324.735

¹ The composition of the index undergoes an annual review, contingent upon adherence to criteria concerning social, societal, and governance aspects. Certainly, the incorporation of new entries and the removal of existing ones enable changes in its composition from year to year.

COUSUMAR	03/06/1985	Agri-food	Yes	5.211.700.000,00	94.487.143
LafargeHolcim	19/02/1997	Building materials	Yes	10.605.254.000,00	23.431.240
MANAGEM	11/07/2000	Mines	Yes	4.494.600.000,00	9.991.308
SALAFIN	17/12/2007	Finance companies	No	1.010.812.000,00	3.124.119
SMI	18/06/1997	Mines	No	1.284.755.441,44	1.645.090
SODEP	19/07/2016	Transport services	Yes	2.141.266.000,00	73.395.600
SONACID	02/07/1996	Building materials	Yes	1.814.319.000,00	3.900.000
TAQA MOROCCO	24/12/2013	Electricity	Yes	6.906.175.000,00	23.588.542
TotalEnergies	29/05/2015	Oil and Gas	Yes	2.299.078.000,00	8.960.000
IAM	13/12/2004	Telecommunications	Yes	18.800.000.000,00	879.095.340

Source: The data presented is credited to authors who relied on information sourced from the Casablanca Stock Exchange, <https://www.casablanca-bourse.com/fr/bourse-de-casablanca-sa>. [Accessed: March 2024]

The assignment of a rating to a company facilitates its categorization based on the mentioned criteria. The evaluation (ESG rating) is calculated using algorithms that vary from one rating agency² to another. Traditionally, the most popular financial rating agencies, namely S&P, Moody's, and Fitch, provide their expertise in financial analysis by relying solely on data extracted from reports and summary documents of companies' financial situations, in order to offer their services to various users, including investors who, based on their risk aversion levels, make decisions by incorporating the two classic parameters, risk and return expectations. Currently, in addition to financial criteria, these agencies have strengthened their analytical capabilities by considering ESG rating.

Following this trend, Morocco has embarked on a sustainable development perspective, requiring a widespread adoption of financial reporting methods that combine financial and extra-financial information. To achieve this, it relies on the same service providers who now opt for integrated measurement tools that respect both types of information (de Boissieu, 2023).

The efforts made to promote a new socially responsible analysis method have resulted in the creation of the first ESG 10 index composed of 10 stocks that have obtained the highest extra-financial ratings. The launch of this index by the Casablanca Stock Exchange in collaboration with the extra-financial rating agency Viego EIRIS on 27/09/2018 (Lagsir and Moflih, 2020), signaled a shift towards an investment approach that prioritizes adherence to sustainability framework within a broader perspective of global development.

3. Event study methodology

This study seeks to investigate how the market reacts to a specific event, namely, how investors respond to the announcement of the reinforcement of the MASI-ESG index. At the onset of the event study, the initial step is to define the event date t_0 and to identify the event window, which denotes the period for examining the stock prices of relevant companies (Flammer, 2013). Within this research, the event date is designated as January 24, 2023, corresponding to the day when the Casablanca Stock Exchange unveiled the expansion of the "MASI-ESG" index to 15 stocks, an increase from the previous 10. Given the premise that investors might require a period to respond to the event and circumvent uncertainties associated with it (MacKinlay,

² In the traditional sense, a rating agency is an independent private entity responsible for evaluating a company's creditworthiness through the assignment of a rating, thus giving rise to the term "rating". Over 90% of the global rating agencies market is controlled by just three entities—S&P, Moody's, and Fitch—highlighting the substantial concentration within the market.

1997), we will set our time span at 5 days $(t_1; t_2) = (-2; 2)$. The market sensitivity is represented by the stocks' abnormal return around the event day. It corresponds to the difference between the price of a stock and its expected value (Flammer, 2013).

Researchers, especially in the field of finance, have employed different models like the market model, the mean-adjusted model, and the market-adjusted model (Fernando and Guneratne, 2009) to gauge the abnormal returns of a stock during a specific timeframe. In this study, we have chosen the market model to estimate abnormal returns for companies listed on the MASI-ESG. Besides being consistent with the majority of event studies (Yadav et al., 2016), the market model offers the benefit of considering beta (β) variation, unlike the market-adjusted model, which assumes a $\beta = 1$ for each stock, and the mean-adjusted model, which ignores market-wide stock price fluctuations. If there's movement on the event day, it could lead to biased results.

The market model defines abnormal returns (AR) by the following formula:

$$AR_{it} = R_{it} - (\alpha_i + \beta_i R_{mt})$$

With:

- AR_{it} = abnormal return of the asset (i) on the day of the event (t);
- R_{it} = real return of the asset (i) on the day of the event (t);
- β_i = market risk associated with the asset (i) compared to the market index;
- R_{mt} = Return of the benchmark index on the day of the event (t);
- α_i = coefficient of variation.

Furthermore, given that the event took place simultaneously for all companies listed on the MASI-ESG, the estimation of market reaction will be estimated using standardized cumulative abnormal returns (SCAR) rather than cumulative abnormal returns (CAR). The aim is to prevent cross-sectional correlation, as indicated by studies conducted by Coutts et al. (1995), Campbell et al. (1997), Kolari and Pynnönen (2010), and Pacicco et al. (2018).

$$SCAR_i(T_1, T_2) = CAAR_i(T_1, T_2) / s_i$$

With:

$$CAAR_i(T_1, T_2) = \text{cumulative average abnormal returns}$$

$$CAAR_i(T_1, T_2) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=0}^N CAR_i$$

s_i = standard deviation estimated by:

$$s_i = \sqrt{\frac{1}{T_2 - T_1} \sum_{t=T_1}^{T_2} (AR_{it} - \overline{AR}_i)^2}$$

With:

\overline{AR}_i : The average of the time series of abnormal returns for firms i over the period (T_1, T_2)

$$\overline{AR}_i = \frac{1}{(T_2 - T_1) + 1} \sum_{t=T_1}^{T_2} AR_{it}$$

For the significance test (ST) of abnormal returns, we will use the following formula:

$$t = \frac{AAR_t \sqrt{N}}{\sigma AAR_t}$$

With:

σAAR_t : Standard deviation

For cumulative abnormal returns, the statistic is:

$$t = \frac{CAAR_t}{\sigma AAR_t \sqrt{\text{number of days}}}$$

4. Empirical Results

In this section, we will outline the results of the event study, which involves estimating the market model following the research methodology, prior to determining the average abnormal returns (AARs) and cumulative average abnormal returns (CAARs). Afterward, two statistical tests based on a Student's t-distribution will be conducted to examine the abnormal returns, ensuring their statistical significance and facilitating meaningful discussion of the findings.

4.1 Estimation of the market model

Table number n°2 indicates the estimated parameter values of the market model for the 15 firms comprising the corporate social responsibility benchmark index.

Table n°2: Parameter values of the market model for the returns of companies constituting the MASI-ESG

BMCI			R2=0,11	F-stat =69,39
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
Alpha	-0.001042	0.000825	-1.262781	0.2072
BETA	1.023649***	0.122878	8.330635	0.0000
BOA			R2 =0,27	F-stat =191,60
Alpha	0.000308	0.000451	0.682577	0.4952
BETA	0.930389***	0.067215	13.84204	0.0000
AWB			R2 =0,60	F-stat =770,58
Alpha	-5.29E-05	0.000317	-0.166800	0.8676
BETA	1.310727***	0.047217	27.75949	0.0000
BCP			R2 =0,47	F-stat =453,93
Alpha	-5.78E-05	0.000365	-0.158413	0.8742
BETA	1.158025***	0.054353	21.30570	0.0000
CIH			R2 =0,06	F-stat =31,48
Alpha	0.000416	0.000649	0.641617	0.5214
BETA	0.541765***	0.096545	5.611533	0.0000

COUSUMAR			R2 =0,00	F-stat =0,88
Alpha	-0.000390	0.000751	-0.519270	0.6038
BETA	0.105255	0.111775	0.941670	0.3468
LAFARGE			R2 =0,36	F-stat =286,20
Alpha	-7.49E-05	0.000570	-0.131501	0.8954
BETA	1.434385***	0.084786	16.91764	0.0000
MANAGEM			R2 =0,08	F-stat =44,77
Alpha	0.001588	0.000707	2.245315	0.0252
BETA	0.704469***	0.105275	6.691707	0.0000
SALAFIN			R2 =0,02	F-stat =9,14
Alpha	0.000360	0.000865	0.416315	0.6774
BETA	0.389479***	0.128814	3.023570	0.0026
SMI			R2 =0,00	F-stat =3,74
Alpha	-0.000630	0.000933	-0.675274	0.4998
BETA	0.268558*	0.138849	1.934174	0.0536
SODEP			R2 =0,30	F-stat =228,90
Alpha	0.000144	0.000516	0.279678	0.7798
BETA	1.162347***	0.076826	15.12961	0.0000
SONACID			R2 =0,02	F-stat =10,62
Alpha	0.001145	0.000915	1.250890	0.2115
BETA	0.444069***	0.136241	3.259427	0.0012
TAQA			R2 =0,11	F-stat =63,67
Alpha	0.000301	0.000770	0.390398	0.6964
BETA	0.914499***	0.114606	7.979536	0.0000
TOTAL			R2 =0,14	F-stat =82,48
Alpha	-1.66E-05	0.000654	-0.025432	0.9797
BETA	0.884586***	0.097397	9.082231	0.0000
IAM			R2 =0,40	F-stat =358,90
Alpha	-0.000600	0.000318	-1.884835	0.0600
BETA	0.897279***	0.047363	18.94481	0.0000

*, **, *** Indicate significance levels of 10%, 5%, and 1%, respectively.

Source: Authors

We note the significance of Beta coefficients across all securities, ranging from 0.26 for the 'SMI' security to 1.43 for the 'Lafarge' stock, except for the 'Cousumar' value, where the Beta coefficient of 0.10 is deemed non-significant. When the threshold is set at 5%, we observe that this parameter serves as a significant estimator of systematic risk.

The Alpha, also known as the model constant, was determined to be insignificantly different from 0. This outcome isn't surprising given that, in modern portfolio theory, if market returns are zero, the returns of the security should align with those of a risk-free asset. Thus, it's expected that this would have minimal impact on measuring daily returns since risk-free daily returns naturally approach zero rates.

The Fisher statistic's value rejects its null hypothesis of simultaneous nullity of all coefficients, except for the 'Lafarge' stock. At the 5% significance level, the probabilities linked to the F-statistic support an overall significance of the model.

Furthermore, an examination of the coefficients of determination R2 indicates a good quality of fit by the model for the IAM, SODEP, LAFARGE, ATW, BCP, CIH, and BOA stocks, with R2 values varying between 27% and 60%.

Generally speaking, we recognize the current findings from the market model estimation as a crucial step in the computation of abnormal returns associated with the focal event.

4.2 Evolutions of abnormal returns

In accordance with extensive literature, theoretical returns have been estimated using the market model. The study of modifications in the securities returns within the selected interval $I = (-10d; +10d)$ indicates a positive average abnormal return of 0.1% (Table n°3).

Tableau n°3: Returns of securities within the interval (-10, +10)

Interval	AAR	CAAR	t_AAR	t-CAAR
-10	-0,006	-0,006	-4,697***	-1,405*
-9	-0,001	-0,007	-0,695	-1,603*
-8	0,013	0,005	9,413***	0,753
-7	0,011	0,016	8,102***	2,528***
-6	0,005	0,021	3,732***	4,355***
-5	-0,003	0,019	-2,002**	3,098***
-4	-0,002	0,017	-1,199	5,394***
-3	-0,003	0,014	-2,129**	3,819***
-2	-0,002	0,012	-1,302	3,648***
-1	0,001	0,013	0,495	4,165***
0	0,001	0,014	0,458	5,269***
1	-0,001	0,013	-0,680	2,343**
2	0,002	0,015	1,244	2,902***
3	-0,003	0,012	-2,136**	2,493**
4	0,008	0,019	5,697***	4,663***
5	0,003	0,023	2,447**	4,458***
6	0,003	0,026	2,386*	6,228***
7	-0,006	0,020	-4,494***	3,936***
8	0,004	0,024	2,861***	5,719***
9	0,002	0,026	1,548*	6,377***
10	-0,004	0,022	-2,854***	4,687***
Average	0,001	0,015		

***, **, and * indicate statistical significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively.

Source: Authors

The (CAARs) recorded positive values with an average (CAAR) of 1.15% over the same 21-day window. In the case of CAARs, positive results are more pronounced compared to the (AARs) beginning from the eighth day before the event announcement (D_{-10+2}).

Graph No. 1 showcases the (ARs)' evolution over a 21-day period, demonstrating an overall positive trend specifically on the eighth and seventh days preceding the announcement. Afterward, there is a period of brief stability around the event day before the return to a positive trend on the 15th day, which is then succeeded by a negative decline after the

18th day, culminating in complete nullification precisely 10 days subsequent to the announcement of the new introductions to the reference index under examination.

Graph n°1: Evolution of ARs_t of index values

Graph n°2 reflects the evolution of (AARs) over the 21-day window. In the general run of things, three instances of positive peaks in profitability occur on days d-7, d+6, and d+9, with a singular negative peak on d+8. Over a four-day window around the event date, there was relative stability; indeed, graphically, it appears that the theoretical returns do not deviate from those actually observed in the market.

Graph n°2: Evolution of AARs:

The evolution graph of CAARs exhibits a notable and positive trend starting from day -8, followed by a minor decline between day -5 and day +4, before reverting to the initial positive trend until the final day of the period (21st day).

Graph n°3: Evolution of CAARs

Looking at the broader timeframe of 21 days surrounding the announcement date, the reaction to the event has been positive, with a brief period of neutrality occurring three to four days around the event itself. To affirm the identified investors' reaction, the analysis incorporated the review of two statistics that, given normality, adhere to a Student's t-distribution with N-1 degrees of freedom, with N representing the total number of companies involved in the event.

The values of abnormal returns and cumulative abnormal returns are presented in Table No. 3, along with their corresponding Student's t-statistics.

The t-stats show significance at N-1 degrees of freedom for abnormal returns spanning from d-9 to d-6, as well as from d+4 to d+8 and d+10. The most significant returns are those related to the third (d-8) day of the event window and those occurring on the fourth day after its announcement date (d+4). Drawing upon these results, it becomes evident that there was a short-term investor reaction characterized by predominantly positive abnormal returns, indicating the shareholder value creation in the very short term in response to the event examined in this study.

Regarding (CAARs), the t-statistic values displayed tend to support a positive overall reaction from investors. As a matter of fact, starting from d-7, all the values of the statistic associated with the test are significant at the 5% threshold, including the day of the event announcement.

5. Conclusion

The findings of the event study are in line with several earlier research efforts investigating investor reactions to public event announcements. These results can primarily be explained by the effect of information arrival on the behavior of very short-term investors, with a focus on the role of market sentiment, considering that rationality implies the absence of reaction in the very short term for a rational agent.

As part of tests on semi-strong informational efficiency, event studies were introduced as a tool for analyzing fluctuations in stock prices. As a result, we can state that the index under consideration exhibits information inefficiency. Indeed, efficiency maintains that even when information is publicly disclosed, the resulting returns do not exceed or fall significantly below those generated by a benchmark model, namely, the market model.

The conclusions drawn from this study unequivocally demonstrate a broadly positive effect on the index's profitability following new introductions. However, they also indicate that these are rather irrational reactions from investors. To measure the real impact on stock prices and returns, it's vital to consider the medium and long-term perspectives, analyzing potential synergies and their influence on the financial health of companies included in the ESG index.

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